

Living labs as instrument for societal change: the role of intermediary actors and activities

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Abstract

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1 Introduction

Science and innovation policy are increasingly focused towards societal challenges such as climate change (SDG 13), sustainable mobility (SDG 11) and clean energy (SDG 7). Whilst the EU can be seen as a frontrunner in this recent policy shift, national and regional governments are also refocusing their science and innovation policy efforts towards societal challenges. This requires not only science to rebalance their efforts but also a more proactive government (Mazzucato, 2017), as well a transformation of governance arrangements and policy instruments (Kuhlmann & Rip, 2014). Here, we are interested in one instrument for such innovation policy for societal challenges, so-called ‘living labs’. In an earlier study on living labs in the Netherlands (Maas et al., 2017) we developed a fourfold typology of different kinds of living labs. We argued only one of these types was especially suitable to contribute to societal challenges, namely the type which takes place in real-life environments and focuses on co-creating solutions with a wide variety of actors. However, we also saw a lack of learning within and between these kinds of living labs and only marginal attention for upscaling of initiatives and learning experiences. We contend that upscaling, both in terms of replication of knowledge in other places as well as in terms of institutionalization of knowledge in new rules and practices, is a crucial element for living labs to be useful as instruments of innovation policy for societal challenges. However, someone, both individual actors or organizations, is needed who takes responsibility for upscaling and is able to move beyond local, context specific initiatives. By intermediating these actors can play an important role in transitions towards societal change. As Kivimaa and colleagues (Kivimaa et al., 2017a) show, transitions require an ecology of different kinds of intermediaries at different moments in time. These intermediaries take on a whole range of activities, some within a narrowly defined field or sector, others have broader goals and activities. In this research we specifically focus on this role of intermediary actors which leads us to ask the research question of *how can intermediary actors contribute to societal transitions by upscaling local experiments, such as living labs?*

To answer these questions, we use a short literature review and we look at ‘historical’ examples in which local knowledge had to be transformed and re-embedded in different contexts. Both the literature review and the historical examples are still work in progress and we aim to present our preliminary results.

Later in the process, but beyond the scope of the current paper, we will use an exploratory qualitative case study approach to look at three domains in which societal transitions are deemed necessary to take place in the Netherlands: healthcare, circular economy and a low-carbon economy. Within these three domains we aim to look at how several living lab initiatives and intermediary activities are operating in practice. For each case we conduct in-depth interviews with participants, policy-

makers, managers and stakeholders complemented with desk study of project plans, websites, policy documents and other materials.

At the conference we aim to first discuss our interpretation of intermediation and upscaling in the other domains and, second, show some first results from the interviews. As we are in the midst of doing the case studies at that moment, we are open to suggestions and discussion on both the first results and the research purpose.

2 Living labs in theory

Despite the rising attention for living labs, a clear reference point for what a living lab entails is yet missing from the discussion (Schoorman, 2015). One attempt at a comprehensive definition is found in Schliwa and McCormick's (2016) description of living labs as "physical arena as well as a collaborative approach in which different stakeholders have space to experiment, co-create and test innovation in real-life environments defined by their institutional and geographical boundaries". Crucial keywords in this definition are collaboration/co-creation and real-life experimentation. The involvement of citizens is often seen as central to what distinguishes living labs from other forms of public-private partnerships for research and innovation. The European Commission has referred to living labs as 'public-private-people partnerships (EC 2016, our emphasis), others choose terms such as 'quadruple helix' to indicate that the 'triple helix' of science, industry and government is supplemented by citizens as a fourth group (Carayannis and Campbell, 2009). Nonetheless, as Schliwa and McCormick (2016) note, there is a distinction between people involved in their capacity of (potential) user of the innovation and people involved in their full capacity of "citizen", the latter suggesting a higher degree of co-creation, which in turn means that laypersons are able to put their needs and preferences front and centre.

Furthermore, living labs are characterized by the fact that the environment in which this co-creation takes place shifts to the 'real world'. In this respect, living labs answer the call for research and innovation that incorporates real-life complexity. Such a role for what Callon and Rabearisoa (Callon and Rabearisoa, 2003) have called 'research in the wild' has previously been documented for urban studies (Gieryn, 2006) and economics (Levitt and List, 2009). Bringing together a wider set of collaborators in a 'wild' setting results in an increasingly 'hybrid' form of knowledge that is produced, including attention to non-technological aspects to innovation such as regulation, public acceptance, and business models. This shift to real-world research is accompanied by a number of ethical questions. To what extent are practices of prior informed consent maintained in such a setting? What is a

responsible way of involving citizens in research, respecting e.g. their privacy and safety? But also, an experiment always involves some intervention in the world, which means it is important to critically examine their embedded politics (Karvonen and van Heur, 2014).

This last point is especially important in light of the third aspect: the involvement of local government. There are two reasons for this. Pragmatically, local government often bears responsibility for public space, so that living labs' explicit inclusion of local context requires some form of cooperation with local government. But recent years have also seen local government actively take up a role as 'change agent' (Barber, 2013; Bulkeley and Castán Broto, 2013). From this perspective, experiments are an element of urban development strategies (Evans et al., 2016; Evans and Karvonen, 2014). A prominent example are 'smart city' experiments employing digital technology for urban policy; experiments that have been the subject of fierce debate on whose interests they serve, and how to safeguard public interests (Kitchin, 2014; Townsend, 2013; Viitanen and Kingston, 2014).

3 Upscaling living labs

The fact that living labs take place in a real-life experimental environment with extensive involvement for local stakeholders means they are very well rooted in the local context. This is important for ensuring that the solution will 'work' in this context, but poses challenges for wider societal change. Whereas too little attention to local context means that the solution does not fit the problem, a number of contemporary challenges are calling for transformative change on the short rather than the long term, meaning that cross-locational learning is important as a way of accelerating change. In this section we briefly reflect on some theoretical perspectives on how living labs can contribute to societal change, which provides the basis for our ongoing empirical research.

From the field of transition studies, we can gain insight in the way living labs may lead to change by seeing them as 'niches'. These are radical innovations that take place protected from market selection, and are often situated against the dominant socio-technical system ('regime') and factors that are slow-changing and considered external to this system ('landscape') (Geels, 2002). A more transformative shift in the wider system can then be achieved through aggregated and comparative learning obtained by linking together various niches with other developments at the regime and landscape level (Schot and Geels, 2008). An important question is whether a niche is made competitive within an existing selection environment ('fit and conform'), or whether it can catalyse change in this environment that works in the niche's favor

(‘stretch and transform’), which could open up space for more radical innovation (Smith and Raven, 2012). From this perspective the coordination between various levels of government deserves particular attention, because their actions are influential in both these processes of empowerment.

A difficulty with this transitions perspective is that it has little to say about scale; implicitly it often seems to take the ‘regime’ to be on the national scale, and ‘niches’ to be occurring at city-level (Bulkeley et al., 2014). However, the question of the scale on which living labs aspire to create change is an open one. Many of the actors involved are not per definition motivated by grand society-wide goals but are satisfied with making adjustments in their immediate surroundings. This is especially the case for involved citizens and municipal governments. We might expect corporations and knowledge institutes to have a greater interest in the bigger picture, as it implies new business and transferable knowledge for these actors, respectively. Learning then might take place in different networks (e.g. more international) and for different motives (e.g. global city aspirations). Literature on policy mobilities provides useful insights by shifting the focus to the work that is done in the process of policy (knowledge) travelling and being re-embedded in different contexts (McCann and Ward, 2012; Peck, 2011). This perspective explicitly takes the (micro)politics of these mobilities into account, for instance by considering the discourses that are being mobilized to push for the ‘export’ or ‘import’ of certain approaches.

A specific perspective on upscaling sustainability experiments is provided by Naber et. al. (2017) who distinguish between four patterns of upscaling. The first pattern is growing the experiment at the specific places and thereby widening the area of the number of actors involved. Second, they distinguish a replication pattern whereby the experiment is replicated at different locations or in different contexts. A third pattern is that of accumulation whereby the experiments are explicitly linked to other initiatives. Finally, they see a pattern of transformation whereby the experiment shapes the sets of norms, habits and routines on a regime level.

4 Intermediary activities

A central part of the policy mobilities literature is the emphasis on who does the work to decontextualize and re-embed the policy. Similarly, within transition studies there is growing attention for the role of intermediary actors in the process of upscaling. Although there has been a long standing interest in innovation studies in the role of actors who develop and maintain networks through which knowledge can be spread (Howells, 2006), more recently attention has been focused upon the role of intermediaries that are specifically focused on transitions (Kivimaa et al., 2017a).

These transition intermediaries differ from more traditional ones in having a clear idea of the direction of innovation. It is not about spurring innovation in general, but instead they focus upon a specific field for which innovation is needed. Kivimaa and colleagues (2017; p. 12) differentiate between different kinds of roles that transition intermediaries can play on different levels:

- i) a systemic or strategic intermediary operating on all scales and taking a system perspective on change;
- ii) a regime intermediary that is tied through, for example, institutional arrangements or interests to the established regime but has a specific mandate or goal to promote transition and, thus, interacts (often with a range of) niches;
- iii) a niche intermediary typically working to experiment and advance niche activities as part of a particular niche but also trying to influence the regime level for that niche's benefit;
- iv) a process intermediary that facilitates a change process or a project without explicit individual agency or agenda, but may work to advance priorities set externally by other actors; and
- v) a user intermediary translating new technologies to users and user preferences to developers, and qualifying the value of technology offers available.

Some intermediaries are established specifically for this transition task, whereas often these are organizations or individuals who carry out these intermediary activities from within existing organizations. Furthermore, a transition requires an ecology of different kinds of intermediary actors and activities at different moments in time (Hyysalo et al., 2018; Kivimaa et al., 2017a). In this ecology the interconnected actors each fulfill different functions to contribute to the upscaling process.

The nature of the activities of intermediary actors is diverse. They can be involved in articulating demands and expectations, building and maintaining networks, and facilitating learning processes. These activities materialize in activities such as organizing conferences and site visits, the writing of handbooks, setting standards and procedures and conducting monitoring and evaluation (Boon et al., 2011; Boon and Edler, 2018; Kivimaa, 2014; Matschoss and Heiskanen, 2017). One of the central questions within this discussion about intermediaries is how an ecology of experiments and intermediary organizations would look like. Which types of experiments are needed (Kivimaa et al., 2017b)? Which type of intermediary organizations can contribute to upscaling of experiments (Kivimaa et al., 2017a)? And what is the role of different kinds of quadruple helix stakeholders in stimulating this ecology (firms, governments, universities and societal organizations)? These questions, together with the four patterns of upscaling from the previous paragraph,

provide input to a preliminary heuristic (table 2) to look at how intermediation and upscaling can take place.

Table1. Heuristic of intermediation per type of upscaling pattern

	Type of intermediary	Role of intermediary	Activities of intermediary
Growing	Niche intermediary User intermediary	Scaling the experiment in a specific place.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network building within a city • M&E of experiment
Replication	Regime intermediary Process intermediary	Translating the experiment to a different place.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External networking • M&E of experiment • Organising and documenting learning
Accumulation	Systemic intermediary Regime intermediary	Linking knowledge and experience with other initiatives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External networking • M&E of experiment • Organising and documenting learning • Organizing learning visits • Organizing conferences
Transformation	Systemic intermediary	Shaping wider institutional change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External networking • M&E of experiment • Organising and documenting learning • Organizing learning visits • Organizing conferences • Writing handbooks • Developing rules and regulations

5 Upscaling and intermediation in historical examples

If we want to understand how upscaling and intermediation are taking place within current living labs we face the problem that many living labs have only recently been started and the local experiment is still ongoing. In most cases there is not yet much to scale-up, although there are always exceptions. But scaling up and the role of intermediaries is not an issue that is exclusive to living labs, there have been earlier domains and areas where the issue of scaling up local knowledge and experiments played a role and where solutions have been found to deal with this issue. Particularly we have looked at three domains in which these issues have been at stake: in the agricultural sector in the Netherlands, in the Water sector in the Netherlands and in development studies at large. For each of these domains we have documented what role scaling played here and how intermediary activities have played a role in

fostering this scaling process.

Agriculture

The importance of a self-sustaining agricultural sector became an important policy goal in the Netherlands in the years after the second World War. For this goal to be realized the competitiveness and efficiency of production of Dutch agriculture needed to be improved. This led to the development of the so-called OVO-triptych in which Research (Onderzoek), Counselling (Voorlichting) and Education (Onderwijs) came together in which new knowledge was developed by research institutes, for example in experimental gardens and experimental farms, then this knowledge was actively disseminated by counsellors to the farmers. These counsellors functioned as an intermediary between research and the workplace whereby they also collected problems and issues from farmers that could inform researchers about their next projects. This model functioned very well until the 1980s after which there came more attention for issues such as environmental degradation and animal welfare together with an improvement of the education levels of farmers. This led on the one hand to a diversification of policy goals and more discussion about the direction of knowledge an innovation for agriculture and at the same time farmers were now better educated and better able to critique and discuss research results, In response to this development one of the projects that were initiated was called Transform in which a more co-creative approach was taken whereby researchers, farmers, government representatives and societal organisations together worked on, for example, new stable concepts for pigs and environmentally friendly and animal friendly stables for chickens. Within this new approach a kind of counsellors 2.0 were appointed who functioned as knowledge intermediaries between these different stakeholders. Rather than being counsellors bringing new research results to farms, these knowledge intermediaries orchestrated the coming together of different stakeholders around an innovation challenge.

Upscaling within the agricultural sector thus developed from a linear approach towards a more co-creative endeavour whereby in both cases there was a role for an intermediary actor, but with a very different role. These intermediary actors were dedicated professionals that were specifically trained and appointed for this role.

Water

At the end of the last century it became clear that the water management and coastal defences of the Netherlands were not future-proof. Through a mix of different research and innovation programs, sometimes running in parallel, sometimes consecutively, a knowledge base has been created for technical and organizational

improvements in the water chain (sewers, drinking water, water treatment); renewal of river management, so that rapid water rises cause less nuisance and the ecological value of the rivers is increased; development of new forms of coastal defense and integral and climate-robust water management in cities.

The experiences of the programs in joint knowledge development and innovation are continued in the National Knowledge and Innovation Program Water and Climate and the Knowledge Network Delta Program of the Delta Program Commissioner. The program forms a bridge between science and practice and brings together knowledge about a large diversity of water-related tasks. This ranges from research lines aimed at refining climate models to lines that are aimed at disseminating knowledge about climate-proof cities.

Within each research line, knowledge sharing takes place via, among other things, knowledge newspapers, study days and project visits. In addition, there is an active knowledge sharing program at the level of the Delta Program, in which, among other things, knowledge is made available through so-called 'Delta Facts'. The Delta Program also has a knowledge agenda with questions that are, among other things, being made available to partners such as Rijkswaterstaat and Deltares. Once a year, a broad knowledge conference is organized at the level of the Delta Program. In addition, the NKWK is also part of the international Delta Alliance, an international network of areas located in deltas, aimed at knowledge exchange with the aim of strengthening the resilience of delta areas. This alliance consists of 18 territories in 15 countries.

The water domain is an example of a domain in which knowledge sharing and learning from each other are actively organized from a broadly felt urgency. The national government has taken a leading role in this, but the implementation takes place in a broad partnership.

Development studies

Within the development sector many projects take place on a small, local scale. External financiers or development organizations are often involved in this. Even when these projects prove successful, this does not mean that this success automatically spills over to other local contexts, or is picked up by politicians and policymakers. In addition, support from external financiers and development organizations is often temporary. Because of this, both spreading the success and sustained existence is a challenge.

The above observation has led to a lot of attention within the development sector for how successful projects can be scaled up. Although there are different ideas about

what this scale up entails, a shared urgency is felt to increase the potential impact of small-scale interventions. Instead of continuously adapting one-off (possibly successful) projects and interventions, upscaling should contribute to making better use of successes by broadening and sustaining existing interventions ("multiplier effect"). The link is made with the major societal challenges, as formulated in the MDGs and now the SDGs, which call for joint action and an acceleration in its approach.

One of the most important messages from the development studies community is that the successful scaling up of an initiative requires that structural attention be paid to possible upscaling from the outset. This does not mean scaling up or becoming an end in itself, but it does mean that from the start of a project possibilities for upscaling and creating the conditions under which upscaling can take place are considered. Another consequence of this structural attention for upscaling is the role of knowledge building and reflection in enabling possible, successful, upscaling. Crucial to the success of upscaling efforts is learning. The starting point here is that upscaling is an iterative process. This means that there must be continuous questioning whether the project achieves the intended goals, but also what is needed to scale up any success. This requires a monitoring and evaluation strategy. Results can be used to reflect on visualized scaling-up pathways and to adjust these where necessary.

A final lesson from the development studies community is the attention for building capacity and institutional support. This is related to the other lessons: both a well-founded strategy and the involvement of stakeholders from the beginning (who are not directly involved in the project but can be mobilized at a later stage) contribute to creating support for the concrete scaling up process. . In the development sector, building capacity also means: ensuring that innovative processes can be institutionalized in existing policy structures and pass through any political changes.

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